

Rac-4j

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-3-11-rac-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	10	Acq. Method Set:	20% quanbo
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	XT 3 11 RAC
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	12/2/2021 9:54:28 AM CST		
Date Processed:	12/2/2021 10:47:55 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	9.287	2601871	50.54	160310
2	10.821	2546684	49.46	129546

Asy-4j

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-3-13-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	42	Acq. Method Set:	20% quanbo
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	XT 3 13
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	12/2/2021 10:13:14 AM CST		
Date Processed:	12/2/2021 10:49:18 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	9.433	139566	4.06	8442
2	10.936	3300934	95.94	166038